

Sabermetric Study Survey Results

Because of textual signposts and other Qualtrics features, the question label for each question (e.g. Q5, Q22) **may not be always sequential**. The ordering of the results as presented here represents the actual ordering of the questions.

Q5 - Have you ever practiced data analytics to any extent?

122 Responses

Q6 - How many years of experience do you have in data analytics?

Your best estimate is sufficient.

122 Responses

Q7 - Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent?

That is, analytics on baseball data.

122 Responses

Q8 - How many years of experience do you have in baseball analytics?

78 Responses

Q9 - Do you practice any form of programming or software engineering?

We include a wide range of practice, from building complex software systems to writing database queries in SQL or spreadsheet formulae.

122 Responses

Q10 - How many years of experience do you have in programming?

113 Responses

After this point, we exclude nonprogrammers from the report.

Q13 - On which continent is your professional work based?

105 Responses

Q14 - What is the highest level of formal education you have experienced?

105 Responses

Q15 - If you have graduated from some form of higher education, what are the subjects of your primary degrees?

Multiple selections possible.

105 Responses

Other Social Science

Other Social Science - Text

Analytics

Psychology

psychology

Sociology

Clinical Psychology

Psychology

Sociology

Journalism

Other Engineering

Other Engineering - Text

Industrial

Mechanical Engineering (BS)

Analytics

MS Analytics

Analytics

Electrical

Nuclear

Industrial Engineering

Industrial engineering

Operations Research

Geomatics

Chemical

Aerospace Engineering

Others

Others (if multiple, separate by commas): - Text

Analytics

Analytics

Analytics (MS)

Analytics

Analytics

Analytics

Analytics

Analytics

Analytics (MSA)

Analytics

Analytics

Biology, Analytics

Analytics

Engineering Physics

Structural engineering

Aerospace

Advanced Analytics

Analytics

Biology, Analytics

Analytics

Analytics

Accounting, Analytics

Analytics

neuroscience

Atmospheric Sciences

Exercise Science

Business Analytics, Information
Systems

Journalism

Actuarial Science

Physics

Russian

Philosophy

Spanish

Chemistry

English

Biology

Biophysics

Public Health

Journalism, Law

Data Science, Journalism

Q16 - Are there any subjects relevant to data analytics that you have taught yourself?

"Teaching yourself" includes reading textbooks or self-directed online resources, beyond what has been included in your compulsory education.

Multiple selections possible.

105 Responses

Other Social Science - Text

Psychology

Behavioral economics

Others (if multiple, separate by commas): - Text

Spark

Consulting, communications, project management

social media analytics

Python

Physics

Sabermetrics, Baseball specific data analytics

Sabermetrics SQL course

Machine Learning

Programming

Programming

Programming

Data analytics, data visualization

Maxine learning

Q20 - Please rate the following resources on how important they were to prepare you for the analytics work you've done in the last year.

Total population.

99 Responses

● Not at all important ● Slightly important ● Moderately important ● Very important ● Extremely important

Baseball population.

63 Responses

● Not at all important ● Slightly important ● Moderately important ● Very important ● Extremely important

Q22 - How does the inclusion of the following types of content in documentation affect your choice to use the tool or docs?

Total population

88 Responses

Baseball population.

54 Responses

Q24 - What do you see as the biggest failures in most documentation?

Many of the below can be considered problems, but select only those which you feel you often encounter in your practice.

Multiple selections possible.

88 Responses

Other:

Other: - Text

Not strong enough descriptions about data inputs

difficult to search when you don't know specifically what keywords to search for. In pandas for instance, I may know basically what I want to do, but I have no idea what pandas method/function implements this, and so I have no way to search for it.

Too often, code is written in a non-generalizable manner and it makes it difficult to follow.

Too technical for beginners

Lack use case examples

Q26 - On a typical project, do you work with other people in data analytics?

Multiple selections possible.

84 Responses

Q27 - With how many people do you coordinate directly on a typical project?

49 Responses

With how many people do you coordinate directly on a typical project?	Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data.
0	No
0-2	No
14	No
2	No
2	No
2	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
2	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
2	No
2	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
2	Yes, professionally
2	No
2	No
2	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
2	No
2 to 4	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
2-3	No
2-3	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
2-5	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
3	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
3	No
3	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education

3	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
3	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
3	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
3	No
3-7	No
3/4	No
4	No
4	No
4	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
4	No
4	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
4	No
4	No
4	No
4	Yes, professionally
5	No
5	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
5	No
5	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
6	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
6	No
8	Yes, professionally
8	No
Depends	No
Depends on the project.	Yes, professionally

Q28: How much of your data analytic experience is described by the following management structure (must total 100%)?

Total population

49 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
I receive rigid guidelines or requirements from a manager or client.	0.00	70.00	12.92	16.40	269.01
I receive guidelines from a manager or client but retain some flexibility about how I accomplish it.	0.00	100.00	29.73	24.68	609.30
I balance guidance from a manager or client and my own interests and goal.	0.00	60.00	23.98	18.41	338.75
I set my own goals but receive input from a boss, client, or peers.	0.00	80.00	24.80	20.48	419.35
I receive no external input.	0.00	100.00	8.57	16.32	266.33

Baseball population

21 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
I receive rigid guidelines or requirements from a manager or client.	0.00	60.00	15.71	16.92	286.39
I receive guidelines from a manager or client but retain some flexibility about how I accomplish it.	0.00	65.00	28.10	17.22	296.37
I balance guidance from a manager or client and my own interests and goal.	0.00	50.00	26.19	17.86	318.82
I set my own goals but receive input from a boss, client, or peers.	0.00	60.00	23.57	16.41	269.39
I receive no external input.	0.00	30.00	6.43	9.02	81.29

Q29 - If you receive guidelines from someone else, what do they dictate (more than half of the time)?

Not selecting an option means you choose that detail for yourself.

49 Responses

Q30 - How well do the following statements about a project process describe your experience.

Total population

75 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
I (or my team) scrape or create my own data.	1.00	5.00	3.23	1.24	1.54
I downloaded data that someone else scraped or created.	1.00	5.00	3.35	1.26	1.59
I have (or set) a deadline for project completion.	1.00	5.00	2.96	1.12	1.27
I have data before I know what question to ask.	1.00	5.00	3.36	1.15	1.32
I decide an analytical method I want to use before I have my question.	1.00	5.00	4.24	1.04	1.09

Baseball population

43 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
I (or my team) scrape or create my own data.	1.00	5.00	2.93	1.21	1.46

I downloaded data that someone else scraped or created.	1.00	5.00	3.44	1.21	1.46
I have (or set) a deadline for project completion.	1.00	5.00	3.14	1.15	1.33
I have data before I know what question to ask.	1.00	5.00	3.33	1.20	1.43
I decide an analytical method I want to use before I have my question.	1.00	5.00	3.98	1.21	1.46

Q31 - Before you begin programming, do you spend any time making designs for your analytics scripts or methods?

Multiple selections possible.

75 Responses

Q32 - Do you consult your design while working on your project?

66 Responses

Q33 - Does anyone else look at your design documents?

Multiple selections possible.

66 Responses

Q34 - In what proportion of your projects are you expected to deliver or share the following with your audience or client?

Total population

74 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
The summary of my findings.	1.00	5.00	1.84	1.17	1.38	74
The analytical methodology or techniques I used.	1.00	5.00	3.09	1.23	1.52	74
The scripts or programs I wrote.	1.00	5.00	3.85	1.14	1.29	74
The data I used.	1.00	5.00	3.04	1.46	2.12	74

Baseball population

42 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
The summary of my findings.	1.00	5.00	1.95	1.29	1.66	42
The analytical methodology or techniques I used.	1.00	5.00	3.21	1.24	1.55	42

The scripts or programs I wrote.	1.00	5.00	3.79	1.24	1.55	42
The data I used.	1.00	5.00	3.05	1.51	2.28	42

Q35 - Is there anything else you are expected to deliver with results?

14 Responses

Is there anything else you are expected to deliver with results?	Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data.
Recommendations for future data collection	No
Guidance to ensure adoption of tool or insights, i.e. change management	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
Visualizations	No
Next steps/what the findings could lead to.	No
Design documentation and process flow	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
Recommendations	No
A working application	No
Who else will find the results interesting or to what other data might this technique apply	No
Often my "results" are themselves an intermediate data product of some sort. So I'm not necessarily delivering finished results, I'm delivering some sort of modified data set that somebody else downstream will be working with.	No
Recommendations, next best steps, alternative options, etc	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
Possible actionables moving forward	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
Methodology (if unusual or noteworthy), next actionable steps	Yes, professionally
No	No
Recommendations	No

Q36 - Which of the following tools do you frequently use for your work?

Multiple selections possible.

74 Responses

Q37 - In what ways do you test the validity of your results (more than half the time)? - Selected Choice

74 Responses

Q38 - Do you have any other validation techniques not mentioned above?

Do you have any other validation techniques not mentioned above?	Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data.
Test theoretical conclusions to make sure they work in the field	No
model risk management	No
QA team tests with sample datasets	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
LIME	No
Beta testing by users	No
Where possible, apply new code to old exemplar data to see if it produces the expected results.	No
N/A	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education
No	No
Sampling convergence protocols	Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education

Q39 - In what ways do you back up versions of your work on a computer (more than half the time)?

Multiple selections possible.

74 Responses

Q40 - Do you consciously apply any of the following data mining/analytics processes to your work?

71 Responses

Q40_4_TEXT - Something else: - Text

Something else: - Text

CRISP-DM and Microsoft TDSP

custom process

My own analytics workflow

The following phases were adapted from Mariscal, Gonzalo, Oscar Marban, and Covadonga Fernandez. "A survey of data mining and knowledge discovery process models and methodologies." *The Knowledge Engineering Review* 25.2 (2010): 137-166.

Q41 - How many times per typical project do you carry out phases as described below?

71 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
Planning the project schedule	1.00	5.00	2.65	1.47	2.17
Researching the problem domain	1.00	5.00	1.92	1.11	1.23
Researching the resources available	1.00	5.00	1.85	0.94	0.89
Formulating a question or hypothesis	1.00	5.00	2.08	0.85	0.73

Collecting data sources	1.00	5.00	2.13	0.79	0.62
Cleaning data	1.00	5.00	1.87	1.01	1.01
Identifying relevant data	1.00	5.00	1.79	0.85	0.73
Reshaping data for analysis	1.00	5.00	1.86	1.05	1.11
Designing the analytic approach	1.00	5.00	2.21	1.05	1.10
Choosing an algorithm	1.00	5.00	2.23	1.05	1.10
Building or coding the model	1.00	5.00	1.72	0.92	0.85
Tweaking or debugging the model	1.00	5.00	1.62	0.97	0.94
Evaluating the results	1.00	3.00	1.49	0.63	0.39
Interpreting results	1.00	3.00	1.65	0.69	0.48
Reporting results	1.00	5.00	2.38	0.89	0.80
Automating the analysis for replication	1.00	5.00	2.38	1.28	1.64
Responding to feedback	1.00	5.00	2.21	1.32	1.74

Baseball population

39 Responses

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance
Planning the project schedule	1.00	5.00	2.97	1.56	2.44
Researching the problem domain	1.00	5.00	1.92	1.14	1.30
Researching the resources available	1.00	5.00	1.69	0.82	0.67
Formulating a question or hypothesis	1.00	5.00	2.10	0.87	0.76
Collecting data sources	1.00	3.00	2.13	0.76	0.57
Cleaning data	1.00	5.00	1.95	0.99	0.97
Identifying relevant data	1.00	5.00	1.79	0.85	0.73
Reshaping data for analysis	1.00	5.00	1.85	0.83	0.69
Designing the analytic approach	1.00	5.00	2.31	1.09	1.19
Choosing an algorithm	1.00	5.00	2.26	1.08	1.17

Building or coding the model	1.00	5.00	1.56	0.78	0.60
Tweaking or debugging the model	1.00	5.00	1.62	0.95	0.90
Evaluating the results	1.00	3.00	1.44	0.59	0.35
Interpreting results	1.00	3.00	1.56	0.63	0.40
Reporting results	1.00	5.00	2.41	0.93	0.86
Automating the analysis for replication	1.00	5.00	2.33	1.38	1.91
Responding to feedback	1.00	5.00	2.38	1.44	2.08

Q42 - Which phases take the most time?

71 Responses

Q43 - Which phases cause the most frustration or are the most unpleasant?

71 Responses

Q44 - Which of these barriers, if mitigated, would save you the most frustration? Choose up to 3.

71 Responses

